

Nucleophilic Reactions of 2-Methyl-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinones with 2-Indolinones

R. S. VARMA* and (Miss) PREETI GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007

Manuscript received 10 March 1989, accepted 20 June 1989

2-Methyl-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinone undergoes nucleophilic addition-elimination reactions with different indolinones leading to 2-(3-methylene-substituted-oxindolyl)-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinones (2a-e). Similarly, *N*-methylindolinones react with 2-methyl-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinone to give 2-(3-methylene-1-methyl-substituted-oxindolyl)-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinones (4a-e). Mannich reactions were performed on 2 with formaldehyde and morpholine/piperidine to give 2-(3-methylene-1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl-substituted-oxindolyl)-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinones (3a-e). The compounds have been characterised by ir, nmr and mass spectral data.

IN continuation of our work on the nucleophilic reactions of 2-indolinones², we report herein the nucleophilic reactions of 2-methyl-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinones with 2-indolinones. The 2-methyl group owing to its proximity with two electronegative nitrogen atoms behaving as a nucleophile, adds to 3-carbonyl group of 2-indolinones. The intermediate carbinol thus formed undergoes dehydration to yield 2 (Scheme 1). Thus nucleophilic attack of 2-methyl-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinone with 2-indolinones

Scheme 1

H, b; y=4-Cl, c; y=5-Cl, d; y=6-Cl, e; y=5-CH₃,
Scheme 2

and their *N*-methyl-2-indolinones leads to 2 and 4 respectively. The structures of 2 have been confirmed by preparing suitable morpholino/piperidino-methyl analogs (3; Scheme 2). All the compounds have been characterised by elemental analysis and ir, nmr and mass spectral data (Scheme 3)

Scheme 3

Experimental

2-[3-Methylene(substituted-oxindolyl)-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)]-4-quinazolinone (2): A mixture of 2-methyl-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)-4-quinazolinone¹ (1; 0.005 mol) and substituted-isatin (0.005 mol) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was refluxed on a sand-bath for 3–4 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the resulting crystalline solid was washed well with methanol (Table 1).

2-[(3-Methylene-1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl-substituted-oxindolyl)-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)]-4-quinazolinone (3): To 2 (0.005 mol) dissolved in dimethyl formamide (5 ml) was added formalin (1 ml) and morpholine (1 mol) with stirring. The mixture was then heated on a water-bath for 10 min, and then allowed to remain at room temperature overnight. The resulting solid product was washed with methanol and recrystallised from chloroform–petroleum ether (b.p. 80–100°) (Table 1).

Similarly, different piperidino analogs (Table 1) were synthesised.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Sl no	Compd. no	X	Yield %	M p °C	Mol. formula
1	2a	—	68	>280	C ₂₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄
2	2b	—	65	>280	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
3	2c	—	71	>280	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
4	2d	—	65	>280	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
5	2e	—	71	>280	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄
6	3a	O	61	220d	C ₃₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄
7	3a	CH ₃	61	>260	C ₃₁ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₄
8	3b	O	58	210	C ₃₁ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
9	3b	CH ₃	58	188	C ₃₂ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
10	3c	O	56	>260	C ₃₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
11	3c	CH ₃	55	>260	C ₃₁ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
12	3d	O	59	>260	C ₃₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
13	3d	CH ₃	58	>260	C ₃₁ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
14	3e	O	60	>260	C ₃₁ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄
15	3e	CH ₃	56	>260	C ₃₂ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₄
16	4a	—	55	>260	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄
17	4b	—	51	170–75	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
18	4c	—	52	>260	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
19	4d	—	51	>260	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl
20	4e	—	61	>260	C ₂₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄

* All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

**Compound sl. no. 7, δ 1.48 (6H, (CH₃)₂), 2.5 (4H, N-(CH₂)₂), 3.96 (3H, CH₃), 4.35 (2H, N-(CH₂-N)), 6.9–8.4 (12H, ArH) and 8.9 (1H, CH); sl. no. 8, $\nu_{\max}$ 1730 (C=O ester), 1720 (C=O quinazolinone), 1700 (C=N and C=C), 1610 (C=N, C=C), 1120 (C-O-C) and 770 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); sl. no. 9, δ 1.46 (6H, (CH₃)₂), 2.5 (4H, N, (CH₂)₂), 3.91 (3H, CH₃), 4.34 (2H, N-CH₂-N) and 6.2–8.5 (12H, ArH and CH); sl. no. 10, $\nu_{\max}$ 1720 (C=O ester), 1690 (C=O quinazolinone and indolinone), 1610 (C=N and C=C), 1125 (C-O-C) and 785 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl₂); δ 2.42 (4H, N(CH₂)₂), 3.52 (4H, O(CH₂)₂), 3.88 (3H, CH₃), 4.28 (2H, N-CH₂-N), 6.78–8.15 (11H, ArH) and 8.71 (1H, CH); sl. no. 11, $\nu_{\max}$ 1715 (C=O ester), 1675 (C=O quinazolinone and indolinone), 1600 (C=N and C=C) and 775 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); sl. no. 12, $\nu_{\max}$ 1720 (C=O ester), 1700 (C=O quinazolinone and indolinone), 1620 (C=N and C=C), 1120 (C-O-C) and 780 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); sl. no. 15, $\nu_{\max}$ 1720 (C=O ester), 1700 (C=O quinazolinone and indolinone) and 1620 cm⁻¹ (C=N and C=C); sl. no. 16, $\nu_{\max}$ 1720 (C=O ester), 1700 (C=O quinazolinone and indolinone) and 1610 (C=N and C=C); sl. no. 17, $\nu_{\max}$ 1730 (C=O ester), 1700 (C=O quinazolinone) 1695 (C=O indolinone), 1605 (C=N and C=C) and 770 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); sl. no. 18, δ 3.18 (3H, NCH₃), 3.95 (3H, OCH₃), 6.8–8.4 (11H, ArH) and 8.85 (1H, CH); sl. no. 20, δ 2.21 (3H, ArCH₃), 3.01 (3H, NCH₃), 3.81 (3H OCH₃), 6.7–8.3 (12H, ArH and CH)

2-[(3-Methylene-1-methyl-substituted-oxindolyl)-3-(4'-carbomethoxyphenyl)]-4-quinazolinone (4): A mixture of 1 and substituted-isatins (0.005 mol) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was refluxed on a sand-bath for 3–4 h. The resulting solid was washed with methanol and recrystallised from chloroform (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Head of the Chemistry Department for facilities. Thanks are also due to Dr. R. S. Kapil and Prof. S. P. Singh for analytical/spectral data.

References

- R. S. VARMA and P. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, 65, 802.
- R. S. VARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 344.